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Systematic reviews, background papers and other unpublished evidence considered in the development of recommendations

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Mass drug administration for malaria during emergencies, periods of health service disruption, or epidemics of febrile illness

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Mass drug administration for malaria during emergencies, periods of health service disruption, or epidemics of febrile illness

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Executive Summary

After de-duplication, a total of 859 articles were screened for eligibility. Of these, 846 were excluded at the title/ abstract review stage, and another 11 at the full text review stage, resulting in only 2 articles contributing to the quantitative data. In addition, of the 13 articles that were eligible for full-text review, three explicitly included contextual factors relevant to drivers of MDA acceptability, financial and economic aspects of the intervention, and barriers related to feasibility (Sterk [19], Kuehne [20], Kasereka [21]), and one reported relevant operational outcomes by modelling (Walker [22]).

There are limited data meeting eligibility requirements that document the impact of MDA on malaria-attributable morbidity and mortality, and the certainty of the evidence for all outcomes was very low. Available data demonstrated little to no benefit compared to control groups in number of confirmed malaria cases, number of all-cause hospitalizations, number of hospitalizations secondary to severe malaria, and all-cause mortality.

Acceptability and Feasibility

Based on results of 2 studies, MDA was widely accepted by the community. Challenges to implementation of MDA in the emergency setting include difficulties in accurately estimating the target population, supervising field staff, and inconsistencies in drug supply.

Cost and cost-effectiveness

One study examined cost-effectiveness of MDA at a camp for internally displaced persons in DRC. Based on their assessment that 92% of the treatments provided were unnecessary, MDA cost \$46 per case of malaria treated. This was more than treating all confirmed malaria infections after screening all persons at the camp (\$23 USD per case treated), treating all confirmed malaria infections after screening only symptomatic persons at the camp (\$7 USD per case treated), and treating all confirmed malaria infections after screening household contacts of children diagnosed with uncomplicated malaria (\$25 USD per case treated).

Mathematical Modelling

In a setting of complete disruption of malaria services secondary to Ebola transmission, a six-month campaign using dihydroartemisinin–piperaquine, and achieving 70% coverage (the highest coverage modeled), yielded the highest efficacy.

Therapeutic courses of an antimalarial medicine compared to no medicine for reducing the burden of malaria disease during emergencies or periods of health service disruption

Patient or population: reducing the burden of malaria disease during emergencies or periods of health service disruption

Setting: Areas with malaria transmission during emergencies or periods of health service disruption

Intervention: therapeutic courses of an antimalarial medicine

Comparison: no medicine

Outcomes	Anticipated absolute effects* (95% CI)		Relative effect (95% CI)	№ of participants (studies)	Certainty of the evidence (GRADE)	Comments
	Risk with no medicine	Risk with therapeutic courses of an antimalarial medicine				
All-cause mortality <1 months post MDA all ages	8 per 100,000	5 per 100,000 (5 to 7)	RR 0.68 (0.57 to 0.81)	7540998 (1 observational study)	⊕○○○ Very low ^a	Therapeutic courses of an antimalarial medicine may reduce all-cause mortality <1 months post MDA among all ages but the evidence is very uncertain.
All-cause mortality <1 months post MDA - Under 5's	25 per 100,000	9 per 100,000 (6 to 12)	RR 0.34 (0.25 to 0.47)	1353074 (1 observational study)	⊕○○○ Very low ^a	Therapeutic courses of an antimalarial medicine may reduce all-cause mortality <1 months post MDA among children under 5 but the evidence is very uncertain.
All-cause mortality 1-3 months post MDA - all ages	5 per 100,000	9 per 100,000 (8 to 10)	OR 1.77 (1.54 to 2.04)	11419195 (1 observational study)	⊕○○○ Very low ^a	Therapeutic courses of an antimalarial medicine may increase all-cause mortality 1-3 months post MDA but the evidence is very uncertain.
All-cause mortality 1-3 months post MDA - Under 5's	11 per 100,000	12 per 100,000 (9 to 15)	OR 1.13 (0.87 to 1.46)	2008720 (1 observational study)	⊕○○○ Very low ^{a,b}	Therapeutic courses of an antimalarial medicine may have little to no effect on all-cause mortality 1-3 months post MDA among children under 5 but the evidence is very uncertain.
All cause hospitalizations 0-1 months post MDA	Number of all-cause hospital admissions decreased by between 5% and 21% during the four weeks after the first MDA round and by between 8% and 19% during the four weeks after the second round of MDA. Observed statistically significant changes at only one of eight time points. Data on sample population sizes and from non-MDA control areas were not available, so absolute effects can not be calculated.			(1 observational study)	⊕○○○ Very low ^{a,b}	Therapeutic courses of an antimalarial medicine (MDA) may reduce all-cause hospitalizations 0-1 months post MDA but the evidence is very uncertain.

Therapeutic courses of an antimalarial medicine compared to no medicine for reducing the burden of malaria disease during emergencies or periods of health service disruption

Patient or population: reducing the burden of malaria disease during emergencies or periods of health service disruption

Setting: Areas with malaria transmission during emergencies or periods of health service disruption

Intervention: therapeutic courses of an antimalarial medicine

Comparison: no medicine

Outcomes	Anticipated absolute effects* (95% CI)		Relative effect (95% CI)	№ of participants (studies)	Certainty of the evidence (GRADE)	Comments
	Risk with no medicine	Risk with therapeutic courses of an antimalarial medicine				
Severe malaria hospitalizations 0-1 months post MDA	Change in the number of hospital admissions secondary to severe malaria ranged from a decrease of 31% to an increase of 8% during the four weeks after the first round of MDA, and by 8% to 19% during the four weeks after the second round of MDA. Observed statistically significant changes at three of eight time points. Data on sample population sizes and from non-MDA control areas were not available thus absolute effects could not be calculated.			(1 observational study)	⊕○○○ Very low ^{a,b}	Therapeutic courses of an antimalarial medicine (MDA) may reduce severe malaria hospitalizations 0-1 months post MDA but the evidence is very uncertain.
Parasitologically confirmed malaria 0-1 months post MDA	Point estimates of changes in parasitologically-confirmed malaria cases at health facilities decreased by between 35% and 62% during the four weeks after the first MDA round and by between 26% and 58% during the four weeks after the second round of MDA. All change estimates represented a statistically significant change from baseline. However, reductions in the number of parasitologically-confirmed cases were also observed at all time points in no-MDA control areas during this time. 95% confidence intervals of the estimated changes in both MDA and non-MDA groups overlapped at all but two time points immediately after the first round of MDA. Data on sample population sizes were not available thus calculation of absolute effect was not possible.			(1 observational study)	⊕○○○ Very low ^a	Therapeutic courses of an antimalarial medicine (MDA) may reduce parasitologically confirmed malaria 0-1 months post MDA but the evidence is very uncertain.

*The risk in the intervention group (and its 95% confidence interval) is based on the assumed risk in the comparison group and the relative effect of the intervention (and its 95% CI).

CI: confidence interval; OR: odds ratio; RR: risk ratio

GRADE Working Group grades of evidence

High certainty: we are very confident that the true effect lies close to that of the estimate of the effect.

Moderate certainty: we are moderately confident in the effect estimate: the true effect is likely to be close to the estimate of the effect, but there is a possibility that it is substantially different.

Low certainty: our confidence in the effect estimate is limited: the true effect may be substantially different from the estimate of the effect.

Very low certainty: we have very little confidence in the effect estimate: the true effect is likely to be substantially different from the estimate of effect.

Background

Mass drug administration (MDA) for malaria

Malaria, a parasitic disease transmitted by the female *Anopheles* mosquito is considered endemic in 87 countries worldwide. In 2019, there were an estimated 229 million cases (95% confidence interval [CI] 211-252) of malaria and 409,000 (95% CI 387,000-460,000) deaths due to malaria globally. About 97% of cases worldwide were due to *P. falciparum*, one of four species known to infect humans [1]. Widely used malaria control methods include vector control interventions such as the use of insecticide treated nets (ITNs), case management through prompt diagnosis and treatment of malaria cases, and drug-based prevention including intermittent preventive treatment during pregnancy and seasonal malaria chemoprevention [2].

Mass drug administration (MDA) involves systematically treating a targeted population with an antimalarial drug, regardless of presence of symptoms or known infection frequently repeatedly at regular intervals. MDA may be used with the goal of interrupting transmission, reducing morbidity and mortality, or preventing relapse. By treating a large proportion of a target population, asymptomatic infections may be cleared, and reinfections may be prevented through a post-treatment prophylactic effect, the length of which varies depending on the drug used. The effectiveness of MDA may vary depending on proportion of the targeted population covered, the timing of the intervention related to the high-transmission season, the antimalarial drug used, and coverage of complementary interventions such as vector control [3-5].

The use of MDA in different forms has been used to target transmission since the 1920s and has been researched in varying settings as new antimalarials became available [6]. There are now more settings in which MDA may be an appropriate tool, including more countries approaching elimination and increasing numbers of complex humanitarian emergencies in malaria endemic countries during which there may be excess morbidity and mortality warranting a targeted intervention such as MDA [7, 8].

MDA in emergency settings or during epidemics of febrile illness or malaria

In malaria endemic settings, disruptions in health services due to public health emergencies or natural disasters can have a profound impact on malaria burden in communities. The WHO recommends the use of time-limited MDA during complex emergencies in malaria-endemic areas where health services may be disrupted, and during epidemics of malaria, to rapidly curtail morbidity and mortality [3]. During outbreaks of certain febrile illnesses, it may be important to reduce healthcare seeking for malaria to avoid exposure to diseases such as Ebola or COVID-19 and to reduce the burden on healthcare services. MDA could reduce the number of people needing to seek treatment for malaria. During the Ebola outbreak in west Africa in 2014, there were significant decreases in rapid diagnostic test (RDT) positivity and confirmed malaria outpatient admissions following two rounds of MDA in Sierra Leone [9] and a reduction in self-reported febrile illness following two rounds of MDA in Liberia [10].

Objectives

Main objectives

Main objective

To determine whether people residing in malaria-endemic settings and an area experiencing an emergency, period of health service disruption, or febrile illness epidemic should be given an antimalarial for chemoprevention.

Secondary objectives

1. To summarize contextual factors for MDA during emergency settings, periods of health service disruption, or febrile illness epidemics with respect to evaluation of the outcomes of interest, and the societal implications, impact on equity, resource use, acceptability, and feasibility of the intervention of interest
2. To summarize findings from mathematical studies with respect to the impact of different operational factors on the modeled efficacy of MDA during emergency settings, periods of health service disruption, or febrile illness epidemics, including optimal timing with respect to malaria transmission seasons, number of rounds, time between rounds, minimum coverage, and number of years

Methods

Criteria for considering studies for this review

Types of studies included

For the main objective, studies with the following designs were included:

- Randomized designs
 - Cluster-randomized controlled trials (cRCTs) with at least two clusters per arm
 - Cluster-randomized cross over trials with: (a) at least two clusters per arm and (b) a suitable washout period during which the intervention is no longer applied
 - Cluster-randomized stepped wedge designs with at least four clusters
 - Cluster-randomized factorial designs with at least two clusters per level
- Non-randomized designs
 - Quasi-experimental cluster-controlled trials with at least two clusters per arm
 - Controlled before-and-after studies (CBAs) with (a) a contemporaneous control group
 - Interrupted time series (ITS) studies with: (a) a clearly defined point in time when the intervention occurred, and (b) at least three data points collected both before the first round of mass radical cure and after the last round of mass radical cure, measured at evenly spaced intervals (i.e., monthly)
 - Due to the seasonality of malaria transmission, if pre- and post-intervention data points are measured at different calendar months (i.e., different periods of the transmission season), a sensitivity analysis will be performed to explore the potential bias introduced by including these studies.

- Uncontrolled before-and-after studies or before-and-after studies with historical controls (if included, a sensitivity analysis will be performed)

We excluded studies if we observed the following:

- For studies with a control group:
 - The follow-up periods for the intervention and control periods were not identical
 - The timing of baseline and/or endline surveys differed in intervention and control groups
 - The length of pre- and post-intervention periods differed for ITS studies or pre- and post- intervention periods were not aligned with respect to malaria seasonality (*i.e.*, covered different periods of the malaria transmission season from year to year)
 - Background interventions were not equally implemented between intervention and control arms (*i.e.*, the same set of co-interventions were not available in both arms) or were implemented at different times
- A sub-therapeutic antimalarial dose was administered for MDA

For the secondary objectives, all study designs including qualitative and economic evaluations were considered to synthesize contextual information. Mathematical modeling studies were included to inform operational parameters.

Types of participants

Adults and children living in areas of ongoing malaria transmission or malariogenic potential and experiencing an emergency situation, a disruption in health service, or an epidemic of febrile illness or malaria were included. Examples of emergency situations included:

- Natural disasters or environmental hazards
- Humanitarian crises including political/civil unrest and displacement of populations
- Disease outbreaks, epidemics, or pandemic

Studies aimed at targeting specific age-groups in a defined geographic area at the same time will be included (synchronous administration).

Studies in which chemoprevention in the form of individually-timed intermittent preventive treatment in sub-populations (*i.e.*, pregnant women, children or infants) or seasonal malaria chemoprevention were excluded. Studies in special groups (*i.e.*, refugees and soldiers) were included if they met eligibility criteria and reside in a delimited geographic area.

Types of interventions

Intervention arm

For the purpose of this review, MDA was defined as the direct administration of a full therapeutic course of antimalarial medicine (irrespective of the presence of symptoms or infection) at the same time (synchronous) to the entire eligible population of a defined geographic area (except for those for whom the medicine is contraindicated), irrespective of the presence of symptoms or infection. Studies of individually-timed (asynchronous) chemoprevention or intermittent preventive treatment (IPT) in sub-populations (*i.e.*, pregnant women, children, infants, school-children), or seasonal malaria chemoprevention were excluded. Given the unique circumstances surrounding emergency situations, MDA targeting specific age groups (age-targeted MDA) in a defined geographic area were included if they met other eligibility criteria.

Antimalarials for MDA can include blood-stage schizonticide drugs alone or in combination with a hypnozoiticidal or gametocidal drug, but there were no restrictions on studies included for review based on the specific antimalarials used. However, only studies that provided doses of antimalarials intended for curative purposes were included. A dose greater than the current standard prophylactic dose will be considered as a therapeutic dose (e.g. chloroquine or amodiaquine at 300 mg of base weekly; pyrimethamine at 25 mg weekly; proguanil at 100 mg daily; mepacrine at 300 mg weekly in one dose or 700 mg; weekly in daily doses of 100 mg; and quinine at 325 mg twice a day) [11, 12].

Control arm (for designs with a control group)

The control group for cluster-randomized trials included populations that did not receive MDA or were administered a placebo; the control group for a CBA included populations that did not receive MDA; the control period for an ITS study was the baseline period up to one year prior to the first round of MDA.

Background interventions

Intervention and control arms must have both included the implementation of standard of care, defined according to appropriate practices at the time that the study was conducted and considering the availability in emergency situations. Studies including other malaria co-interventions (e.g., ITNs, IRS, source reduction activities and environmental management, enhanced case management) and non-malaria co-interventions (e.g., mass drug administration campaigns for other neglected tropical diseases including ivermectin and mass nutritional supplementation activities such as vitamin A distribution) were considered if these occur as background interventions in both the intervention and control groups. Ideally, the population coverage levels of all other malaria and non-malaria co-interventions should have been similar in both arms at baseline; any differences were noted during data extraction.

Types of outcome measures

Studies must have reported at least one of the following to be included: an outcome of interest, data on contextual factors, or mathematical modeling results (on variation in operational parameters). For outcomes that specify parasitological confirmation, this could have been detected by malaria rapid diagnostic test (RDT), microscopy, or molecular method such as polymerase chain reaction (PCR).

Outcomes

Outcomes were measured at the population level as MDA is a community-wide intervention. If outcomes were reported for unspecified *Plasmodium* species, the local epidemiology of the study area was used to infer the predominate species.

- **Incidence of confirmed malaria illness:** parasitologically-confirmed clinical malaria infection (with symptoms such as fever) as measured by passive surveillance or in a cohort
- **Incidence of malaria infection:** parasitologically-confirmed malaria infection, *irrespective of symptoms*, from active and/or passive surveillance in a cohort
- **Prevalence of malaria parasitemia:** measured in a cross-sectional survey with parasitological confirmation
- **Prevalence of anemia:** defined by hematocrit < 33% or hemoglobin < 11 g/dL
- **Number of hospital admissions (all-cause and malaria specific)**
- **Number of outpatient visits (all/febrile illness)**
- **Number of cases or incidence of severe malaria**

- **Number of blood transfusions**
- **Mortality (all-cause)**
- **Adverse events**
- **Drug resistance:** the prevalence or frequency of molecular markers associated with antimalarial drug resistance

Among those receiving the intervention:

- **Adverse events**

Contextual factors

Evidence for these contextual factors were summarized.

- **Values and preferences.** This describes the relative importance assigned to health outcomes by those affected by them; how such importance varies within and across populations; and whether this importance or variability is surrounded by uncertainty.
- **Acceptability:** the extent to which those benefiting from an intervention as well as other relevant stakeholder groups consider the *intervention* to be appropriate, based on anticipated or experienced cognitive and emotional responses to the intervention
- **Health equity, equality and non-discrimination:** the extent to which the intervention benefits all populations, does not discriminate against anyone on the basis of sex, age, ethnicity, culture, language, sexual orientation or gender identity, disability status, education, socio-economic status (SES), residence or any other characteristic. This could include whether the benefits and harms are equally distributed and whether the intervention is equally affordable and accessible to all
- **Financial and economic considerations:** the cost, overall economic impact, cost-benefit, and/or cost-effectiveness
- **Feasibility and health system considerations:** barriers to implementation (*i.e.*, resources available, programmatic considerations, existing and necessary infrastructure), interaction with existing health system, need for and use of the existing health workforce (including training)

Operational parameters

Insights from mathematical modeling on how variation in operational parameters alter the effectiveness of mass relapse prevention will be summarized for at least the following parameters:

- Timing of rounds with respect to the transmission season
- Number of rounds
- Spacing of rounds
- Number of years for the intervention
- Coverage
- Adherence
- Dosage

Timing of outcome measurement

The pre-intervention or baseline period was defined as 1-12 months prior to, or period concurrent with, the first round of MDA (with the exception of ITS, which is defined above).

The post-intervention period refers to the period following the *last round* of MDA. For studies with a single round of MDA, the *last round* refers to the period following the round. For studies with multiple rounds, the *last round* refers to the last round that occurred during a given transmission season (last round of the first year).

- Subsequent MDA rounds that were administered in a second year were treated as a new analysis period
- Data points measured in between rounds in a given year (intra-rounds) were analyzed separately

For analysis, data were pooled into the following post-intervention period categories: <1 month, 1-3 months, 4 to <12 months and 12-24 months following the *last round* of MDA. If multiple data points are available within the same period category, then the latest measure was used.

Search methods for identification of studies

Literature searches were not restricted to specific study designs. Systematic review teams included studies that meet eligibility criteria, regardless of language or publication status (published, unpublished, in press, and in progress).

In addition to studies evaluating the efficacy or effectiveness of MDA, we screened all papers from the search for studies which can contribute additional information on acceptability, feasibility, operational considerations, costing, antimalarial drug resistance, adherence to treatment and other factors. Such studies can be of qualitative or quantitative design. Both studies using empirical data and mathematical modeling were included in this review.

Electronic database searches

We searched the following databases using the search terms and strategy described in Appendix 1: Cochrane Infectious Diseases Group Specialized Register; Central Register of Controlled Trials (CENTRAL), published in The Cochrane Library; MEDLINE (Pubmed); EMBASE (OVID); and LILACS. We also searched the WHO International Clinical Trials Registry Platform (ICTRP; <http://www.who.int/ictrp/en/>) and ClinicalTrials.gov (<https://clinicaltrials.gov/ct2/home>) for trials in progress, using “malaria” and “mass drug administration” as search terms. See **Appendix 1** for additional information.

Searching other resources

Reference lists

Additionally, we reviewed the reference lists of all studies and articles identified by the above methods and those listed in review articles [4-6, 13, 14] for additional relevant studies.

Conference proceedings

We searched the following recent proceedings for relevant abstracts: Sixth Multilateral Initiative on Malaria Pan-African Malaria Conference (Durban, South Africa; October 2013), Seventh Multilateral Initiative on Malaria Pan-African Malaria Conference (Dakar, Senegal; April 2018), American Society of

Tropical Medicine and Hygiene (ASTMH) 62nd Annual Meeting (Washington, DC, USA; November 2013), ASTMH 63rd Annual Meeting (New Orleans, LA, USA; November 2014), ASTMH 64th Annual Meeting (Philadelphia, PA, USA; October 2015), ASTMH 65th Annual Meeting (Atlanta, GA, USA; November 2016), ASTMH 66th Annual Meeting (Baltimore, MD, USA; November 2017), ASTMH 67th Annual Meeting (New Orleans, LA, USA; October 2018), and ASTMH 68th Annual Meeting (National Harbor, MD, USA; November 2019).

Researchers and organizations

In addition to the electronic searches described above, we collaborated with the Malaria Elimination Initiative at the University of California at San Francisco and other relevant groups to identify both published and unpublished studies that might be available from other sources. We also contacted the Malaria Eradication Research Agenda Consortium, the Malaria Eradication Scientific Alliance, and the Bill and Melinda Gates Foundation.

Data collection and analysis

Selection of studies

Two reviewers independently screened titles and abstracts identified from literature searches based on the pre-determined inclusion criteria. Any potentially relevant articles identified by at least one reviewer were evaluated by the same two reviewers for full-text eligibility based on the pre-determined inclusion criteria. A third reviewer was consulted to resolve any disagreements by discussion or consensus. At the full-text stage, we collated different publications reporting on the same study. Full-text studies that did not meet eligibility criteria were listed with their reasons for exclusion in a table (**Appendix 1**).

Data extraction and management

Two reviewers independently extracted information from studies on a pre-piloted electronic data extraction form. Any discrepancies in information were resolved by discussion to reach consensus or by consultation with a third reviewer if consensus could not be reached. Original study authors were contacted to retrieve any missing data and for clarifications as needed.

The following information was extracted when available:

- **Study design and setting:** dates of study, location of study, baseline malaria endemicity (prevalence or incidence), description of malaria seasonality, malaria species, vector species, antimalarial drug resistance context, study design type, and statistical power.
- **Participants:** age groups and other demographic features of population included (*i.e.*, pregnancy, nutritional status) and population targeted by arm; degree of geographical isolation of the treated communities from the untreated communities.
- **Intervention:** MDA drug and dose, coverage, timing (number of rounds/campaigns, dates of rounds, duration implemented, and timing relative to malaria transmission season).
- **Outcomes:** definition and measurement (including malaria diagnostic or surveillance method, population in which outcome was measured, and length of follow-up if relevant), time point(s) at which outcome was assessed relative to MDA rounds, sample size, incomplete outcomes or missing data.

- **Contextual factors:** information on contextual factors (as defined under “Types of outcome measures”) was extracted from studies and summarized.

For rate data (incidence and mortality), we extracted the number of events, the total person time at risk or population at risk in each study arm, and a measure of variance (standard error) when available.

Assessment of risk of bias in included studies

Two members of the review team independently assessed the risk of bias for each study that meets eligibility criteria using a tool designed to assess such risk and generating an overall assessment reported as low, moderate, serious, critical or unclear, and summary graphs to display results. As the risk of bias in the effect of an intervention may be different for different outcomes, a ‘Risk of bias’ assessment for each outcome was made. Discrepancies were resolved through discussion or by consulting a third member of the review team.

We assessed risk of bias of included studies using Cochrane Risk of Bias tool modified for non-randomized studies [15].

Strategy for data synthesis

Certainty of the evidence

The certainty of evidence was evaluated using the GRADE approach [16] and each reported outcome was rated as described by Balslem *et al.* [17].

- High: we are very confident that the true effect lies close to that of the estimate of the effect.
- Moderate: we are moderately confident in the effect estimate. The true effect is likely to be close to the estimate of the effect.
- Low: our confidence in the effect estimate is limited. The true effect may be substantially different from the estimate of the effect.
- Very low: we have very little confidence in the effect estimate. The true effect is likely to be substantially different from the estimate of effect.

Using this approach, randomized trials begin as high-quality evidence but can be downgraded for valid reasons within the following five categories: risk of bias, imprecision, inconsistency, indirectness, and publication bias. The certainty of evidence can be upgraded if there is a large effect, a dose response effect, and if all plausible residual confounding would reduce a demonstrated effect or would suggest a spurious effect if no effect was observed [17].

Results

Results of the search

A total of 897 articles were identified from searching electronic databases (740), reviewing previous Cochrane Reviews on MDA (143), and other sources (3). Thirty-eight of the identified articles were found to be duplicate entries; titles and abstracts of 859 articles were screened for eligibility. Of these, 846 were found to be irrelevant, and 13 full-text articles were assessed for eligibility criteria (**Figure 1**). Details of all articles that underwent full-text review can be found in **Appendix 2**.

Figure 1. PRISMA diagram

Excluded studies

Eleven articles were excluded from the review (primary objective) during full text screening due to the following reasons: MDA not administered (4), no relevant outcomes reported (3), insufficient data points for ITS (2), non-humanitarian setting (1), sub-therapeutic dose administered for MDA (1). See **Appendix 2** for additional details.

Included studies – Primary objective

Two articles were included for quantitative assessment of the primary objective. Neither article described a cluster randomized controlled trial. Furthermore, the outcomes reported in each article were unique and reported measurements could not be compared with one another. Descriptive characteristics for the studies reporting empirical data are summarized in **Table 1** and in **Appendix 2**.

Interventions and Settings

The two studies meeting eligibility criteria for inclusion reported outcomes associated with different MDA interventions in different settings. Aregawi *et al.* [18] described the use of two rounds of MDA with artesunate-amodiaquine (ASAQ) provided with a 5-week interval in the setting of the 2014–2016 Ebola outbreak in Sierra Leone. Sterk *et al.* [19] described an MDA campaign consisting of two rounds of ASAQ followed by one round of pyronaridine-artesunate (Pyramax) at approximately 4-week intervals for populations of internally displaced persons in setting of COVID-19 in the Democratic Republic of the Congo. The predominant *Plasmodium* species at both study sites is *Plasmodium falciparum* with high levels of transmission.

Outcomes

Of the pre-identified outcomes of interest, data on the following outcomes were available in the two eligible studies: number of all-cause and malaria-specific hospital admissions (Aregawi) and all-cause mortality (Sterk). Although neither incidence nor study populations were reported, Aregawi *et al.* did report the percent change of the number of parasitologically-confirmed malaria cases seeking care at selected health facilities. Both articles also reported additional findings outside the scope of this review as defined by the outcomes of interest. See **Table 1** and **Appendix 2** for additional details.

Included studies – Contextual Factors

Of 13 articles that were eligible for full-text review, three explicitly included contextual factors relevant to drivers of MDA acceptability, financial and economic aspects of the intervention, and barriers related to feasibility (Sterk [19], Kuehne [20], Kasereka [21]).

Included studies – Operational Parameters/Modelling

Of 13 studies reviewed, one reported relevant operational outcomes by modelling (Walker [22]).

Effects of interventions

Cases of confirmed clinical malaria during MDA and 0-1 months post MDA

Aregawi *et al.* [18] summarized changes in the number of confirmed malaria cases diagnosed at health facilities during and immediately after MDA. Data were presented weekly as a modeled relative changes from baseline up to four weeks following the second and final round of MDA. Number of cases by

Table 1 – Characteristics of studies meeting eligibility criteria for inclusion following full-text review.

Study Author (location, year)	Study design	MDA Intervention		Study population	Outcomes reported†
		Rounds, interval	Population targeted (estimated coverage*)		
Aregawi <i>et al.</i> (Sierra Leone, 2016 [18])	Controlled interrupted time series	2 rounds ASAQ given 5 weeks apart	3,030,532 (90%)	Undefined/unenumerated	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RDT confirmed malaria cases • RDTs used • Test positivity rate • Malaria cases (combined confirmed & unconfirmed) • Proportion outpatient malaria • Non-malaria consults • Ebola alerts • All-cause hospital admissions • Inpatient malaria cases • Proportion inpatient malaria cases
Sterk <i>et al.</i> (DRC, 2021 [19])‡	Non-randomized controlled trial	2 rounds ASAQ followed by 1 round Pyramax; all rounds 4 to 7 weeks apart	53,000 (135%)	5970 intervention, 9424 control	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Self-reported malaria/illness • All-cause mortality • Malaria-specific mortality • Adverse Events (uncontrolled)

* Mean estimated coverage is shown here when estimates provided for multiple rounds of MDA

† Outcomes reported but not included for systematic review are listed in grey

‡ Study is referred to by first author of presentation given at Médecins Sans Frontières Scientific Day Conference 2021. Peer-reviewed manuscript not currently available; data provided by investigators and may not reflect findings ultimately seen in literature.

passive surveillance was not included as an outcome of interest, but as the results are time bound and presented as a relative change from baseline in a likely nearly static population, they are included as a representation of malaria incidence.

Point estimates of changes in parasitologically-confirmed malaria cases at health facilities decreased by between 35% and 62% during the four weeks after the first MDA round and by between 26% and 58% during the four weeks after the second round of MDA. All change estimates represented a statistically significant change from baseline. However, reductions in the number of parasitologically-confirmed cases were also observed at all time points in no-MDA control areas during this time. 95% confidence intervals of the estimated changes in both MDA and non-MDA groups overlapped at all but two time points immediately after the first round of MDA (**Figure 2**). Data on sample population sizes were not available.

Figure 2 – Reported impact of MDA on number of parasitologically-confirmed malaria cases

Risk of bias and certainty of evidence

The evidence for the effect of MDA on parasitologically-confirmed clinical malaria was graded as **VERY LOW**. As data are the result of a study with a non-randomized design, the quality of evidence was initially rated as low, with a subsequent down-grading to very low due to a high risk of bias (**Table 2**). No other modifying criteria were met, including those that would upgrade the quality of evidence (large magnitude, dose response, plausible residual confounders). Justifications for judgements are provided in **Appendix 2**.

Table 2. Components of certainty of evidence for impact of MDA on cases of parasitologically-confirmed malaria.

GRADE by design	Risk of Bias		Overall	Inconsistency	Indirectness	Imprecision	Publication Bias	GRADE
	Domains							
LOW	Eligibility	Low	↓	-	-	-	-	VERY LOW
	Exposure	Uncertain						
	Outcome	High						
	Control for Confounding	Uncertain						
	Follow-up	Low						

High	High risk of bias	↓	Certainty downgraded
Uncertain	Uncertain risk of bias	-	Certainty not downgraded
Low	Low risk of bias		

Number of all-case hospitalizations during and 0-1 months post MDA

Number of all-cause hospital admissions decreased by between 5% and 21% during the four weeks after the first MDA round and by between 8% and 19% during the four weeks after the second round of MDA. Observed changes represented statistically significant changes at one of eight time points (**Figure 3**). Data on sample population sizes and from non-MDA control areas were not available.

Figure 3 – Reported impact of MDA on number of all-cause hospitalizations

Risk of bias and certainty of evidence

The evidence for the effect of MDA on all-cause hospital admissions was graded as **VERY LOW**. Ratings for individual components were similar to those for impact on parasitologically-confirmed malaria cases, with an additional downgrading for imprecision as confidence intervals for most time points presented included the baseline estimate (Table 3). Justifications for judgements are provided in **Appendix 2**.

Table 3. Components of certainty of evidence for impact of MDA on all-cause hospitalizations.

GRADE by design	Risk of Bias		Inconsistency	Indirectness	Imprecision	Publication Bias	GRADE
	Domains	Overall					
LOW	Eligibility	Low	↓			↓	VERY LOW
	Exposure	Uncertain					
	Outcome	High					
	Control for Confounding	High					
	Follow-up	Low					

High	High risk of bias	↓	Certainty downgraded
Uncertain	Uncertain risk of bias	-	Certainty not downgraded
Low	Low risk of bias		

Number of hospitalizations secondary to severe malaria during and 0-1 months post MDA

Change in the number of hospital admissions secondary to severe malaria ranged from a decrease of 31% to an increase of 8% during the four weeks after the first round of MDA, and by 8% to 19% during the four weeks after the second round of MDA. Observed changes represented statistically significant changes at three of eight time points (**Figure 4**). Data on sample population sizes and from non-MDA control areas were not available.

Figure 4 – Reported impact of MDA on number of hospitalizations due to severe malaria

Risk of bias and certainty of evidence

The evidence for the effect of MDA on hospital admissions secondary to severe malaria was graded as **VERY LOW**. Ratings for individual components were identical to those listed above for all-cause hospital admissions (Table 4). Justifications for judgements are provided in **Appendix 2**.

Table 4. Components of certainty of evidence for impact of MDA on hospitalizations secondary to severe malaria.

GRADE by design	Risk of Bias		Overall	Inconsistency	Indirectness	Imprecision	Publication Bias	GRADE
	Domains							
LOW	Eligibility	Low	↓	-	-	↓	-	VERY LOW
	Exposure	Uncertain						
	Outcome	High						
	Control for Confounding	Uncertain						
	Follow-up	Low						

High	High risk of bias	↓	Certainty downgraded
Uncertain	Uncertain risk of bias	-	Certainty not downgraded
Low	Low risk of bias		

All-cause mortality

Data on all-cause mortality presented by Sterk *et al.* [19] demonstrated an overall reduction in mortality for both the overall population and in children under five years in the month immediately following an MDA campaign consisting of two rounds of ASAQ and one round of Pyramax. The effect was no longer apparent at 1–3 months post MDA in either the general population or in children under five years, as point estimates for the mortality in the MDA groups were greater than those that had not received MDA (Figure 5).

Figure 5. All-cause mortality

A. Less than 1 month post-MDA

B. 1—3 months post-MDA

Risk of bias and certainty of evidence

The evidence for the effect of MDA on all-cause mortality at both 0—1 month and 1—3 months post-MDA were graded as **VERY LOW**. Ratings for individual components were identical to those listed above for all-cause hospital admissions. Justifications for judgements are provided in **Appendix 2**.

Table 4. Components of certainty of evidence for impact of MDA on all-cause mortality. Note: grades for individual components are identical for both the < 1 month post-MDA and 1—3 month post-MDA time periods.

GRADE by design	Risk of Bias		Overall	Inconsistency	Indirectness	Imprecision	Publication Bias	GRADE
	Domains							
LOW	Eligibility	Low	↓			↓		VERY LOW
	Exposure	Uncertain						
	Outcome	Low						
	Control for Confounding	Uncertain						
	Follow-up	Low						

High	High risk of bias	↓	Certainty downgraded
Uncertain	Uncertain risk of bias	-	Certainty not downgraded
Low	Low risk of bias		

Contextual factors

Acceptability and reasons cited for non-adherence

Kuehne *et al.* [20] found that MDA was widely accepted by the community during a large-scale campaign in Monrovia, Liberia in 2014. Only one respondent of 222 households surveyed disapproved of MDA due to how the medication was distributed. Among survey respondents, reasons given for not completing all doses of medication provided were “saving it for later”, “not feeling ill”, “not tolerating medication”, “gave it to someone else”, and “waiting for recommended time to pass between rounds 1 and 2”.

Sterk *et al.* [19] also documented high acceptability of MDA despite noting several challenges to implementation in the emergency setting. Accurate estimation of the target population, supervision of field staff, and inconsistencies in drug supply were among the challenges cited.

Cost and cost-effectiveness

Kasereka [21] estimated the cost-effectiveness of MDA used at a camp for internally displaced person in DRC and found that 92% of treatments provided would be unnecessary with a resulting cost of \$46 per

case of malaria treated. This was the highest of both measures for all scenarios considered, including treatment for all confirmed malaria infections after screening all persons at the camp (\$23 USD per case treated), treatment for all confirmed malaria infections after screening only symptomatic persons at the camp (\$7 USD per case treated), and treatment for all confirmed malaria infections after screening household contacts of children diagnosed with uncomplicated malaria (\$25 USD per case treated).

Mathematical Modelling

Walker *et al.* [22] modeled the impact MDA campaigns would have on malaria cases and attributable deaths in 2015 in Guinea, Liberia, and Sierra Leone assuming complete disruption of malaria services secondary to Ebola transmission. In addition to modelling the overall impact of MDA, Walker *et al.* reported how this impact would change in several different scenarios with different coverage of MDA, timing, number of rounds, and medication used. The most effective MDA campaign modeled by the authors was a six-month campaign using dihydroartemisinin–piperaquine and achieving 70% coverage (the highest coverage modeled, Figure 6).

Discussion

There are limited data meeting eligibility requirements that document the impact of MDA on malaria-attributable morbidity and mortality. Available data demonstrated little to no benefit compared to control groups in number of confirmed malaria cases, number of all-cause hospitalizations, number of hospitalizations secondary to severe malaria, and all-cause mortality.

Figure 6. Impact of MDA on malaria cases and deaths in 2015 as modeled by Walker *et al.* Expected malaria cases (A) and deaths (B) in 2015 in Guinea, Liberia, and Sierra Leone combined in the absence of Ebola outbreak (Baseline), with complete disruption of malaria services secondary to Ebola (No intervention), and in the setting of different MDA campaigns with respect to start date, number of rounds (x-axis), and drug used (fill color). A 70% MDA coverage was applied to all estimates. Error bars represent 95% confidence intervals.

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Appendix 1. Search strategy

Search Name: Cochrane Central Register of Controlled Trials

ID	Search
#2	"antimalarial":ti,ab,kw (Word variations have been searched)
#3	malaria:ti,ab,kw (Word variations have been searched)
#4	MeSH descriptor: [Malaria] explode all trees
#5	MeSH descriptor: [Antimalarials] explode all trees
#6	#2 or #3 or #4 or #5
#7	"mass chemoprophylaxis" or "mass drug administration" or "mass administration"
#8	"mass screening and treatment"
#9	"mass treatment"

Database: Embase 1947-Present, updated daily

1	malaria/ or malaria control/
2	antimalarial agent/ or antimalarial*.mp.
3	(malaria or antimalarial*).ab. or (malaria or antimalarial*).ti.
4	1 or 2 or 3
5	("mass chemoprophylaxis" or "mass drug administration" or "mass administration").mp.
6	mass drug administration.mp.
7	mass treatment.mp.
8	"mass screening and treatment".mp.
9	5 or 6 or 7 or 8
10	4 and 9

Pubmed Search history

Search	Query
#1	malaria Field: Title/Abstract
#2	antimalarial*or anti-malarial* Field:Title/Abstract
#3	(malaria[MeSH Terms]) OR antimalarials[MeSH Terms]
#4	#1 or #2 or #3
#5	((mass chemoprophylaxis) OR mass drug administration) OR mass administration Field:Title/Abstract
#6	"mass screening and treatment" Field: Title/Abstract
#7	(MDA[Title/Abstract] OR MSAT[Title/Abstract] OR iMSaT[Title/Abstract])
#8	mass drug administration[MeSH Terms]
#9	#5 or #6 or #7 or #8
#10	#4 and #9

Database : LILACS

Search on:	malaria or antimalarial\$ [Words] and mass administration [Words]
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Appendix 2. Full-text review results

Included Studies

Aregawi et al. 2016 [18]

Study Details

Intervention					Study		
Location	Emergency Setting	Eligibility	Medication Regimen	Dates of Distribution	Primary Sampling Unit	Control	Notes
Sierra Leone (MDA provided to all residents of chiefdoms with confirmed Ebola cases and all zones of Western Area)	Ebola outbreak	All persons \geq 6 months except: (1) malnourished children, (2) pregnant women in first trimester, (3) persons with fever/feeling unwell, (4) persons who received ASAQ in last month, and (5) persons taking Zidovudine, Efavirenz, or cotrimoxazole	<p>Infants: 1 tablet Aresunate 25 mg /amodiaquine 67.5 mg daily for 3 days</p> <p>Children: 1 tablet Aresunate 50 mg /amodiaquine 135 mg daily for 3 days</p> <p>Adolescents: 1 tablet Aresunate 100 mg /amodiaquine 270 mg for 3 days</p> <p>Adults: 2 tablets Aresunate 100 mg /amodiaquine 270 mg for 3 days</p>	<p>Round 1: 5-8 December 2014</p> <p>Round 2: 16-19 January 2015</p>	Health facilities	Persons seeking care at health facilities in areas not receiving MDA.	75 facilities sampled in MDA areas; 16 sampled in control areas. Per the article: "... case series recorded in the selected health facilities are assumed to represent the population living in the respective catchment area."

Certainty of Evidence

Components of GRADE	Risk of Bias Domains	Judgment	Justification
Risk of Bias	Eligibility	Low risk	Eligibility criteria clearly defined
	Exposure Measurement	Unclear risk	Assessment of exposure history based on health facility where individuals seek care; possibility for migration/group cross-over
	Outcome: Malaria incidence	High risk	Outcome measurement relies on care-seeking, case management practices, and record-keeping at health facilities in different geographic locations and in different settings (<i>i.e.</i> , active Ebola cases or not). This method has high risk of introducing bias by an overrepresentation of well-functioning health facilities and persons with access to them
	Outcome: Hospitalization, all cause	High risk	See above justification for general concerns about the risk for introduction of bias from design relying of health facility data from non-randomized and geographically separated facilities. Additionally, no control data for hospitalization (malaria-attributed or all-cause) in control areas due to low availability/reporting. Given the decreased number of cases in both intervention and control groups, the lack of a control group for this measure makes the data difficult to interpret.
	Outcome: Hospitalization, severe malaria	High risk	See justification for all-cause hospitalizations.
	Control for Confounding	Unclear risk	Non-randomized, controlled interventional study
	Follow-up	Low risk	
	Overall	Downgraded	High risk of bias in all outcome measurements, unclear risk of bias in exposure measurement and control for confounding
Inconsistency		-	
Indirectness		-	
Imprecision		Downgraded	Hospitalization measure confidence intervals very large and include null for most time points reported.
Publication Bias		-	

Intervention					Study		
Location	Emergency Setting	Eligibility	Medication Regimen	Dates of Distribution	Primary Sampling Unit	Control	Notes
Democratic Republic of Congo (Angumu Health zone, Ituri province)	Conflict (Internally displaced persons)	All people ages > 2 months eligible except (1) pregnant women in their first trimester, (2) persons with severe malaria, jaundice, or other severe disease, (3) persons with an allergy to the drug being used for MDA, and (4) persons recently treated for malaria	<p><u>Rounds 1 & 2:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Ages 2-11 months: 1 tablet Artesunate Amodiaquine (25mg/67.5mg) daily for 3 days - Ages 1-5 years: 1 tablet Artesunate Amodiaquine (50mg/135mg) daily for 3 days - Ages 6-13 years: 1 tablet Artesunate Amodiaquine (100mg/270mg) daily for three days - Ages ≥14 years: 2 tablets Artesunate Amodiaquine (100mg/270mg) daily for three days <p><u>Round 3:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ages 2-11 months: 1 sachet Pyronaridine tetraphosphate and Artesunate (60mg/20mg) daily for 3 days - Ages 12-48 months: 2 sachets Pyronaridine tetraphosphate and 	<p>ASAQ1: 24 September to 13 October 2020</p> <p>ASAQ2: 9 to 27 November 2020</p> <p>Pyronaridine-artesunate: 17 December 2020 to 8 January 2021</p>	Households	Households in villages and internally displaced person camps were MDA not conducted	MDA and study conducted in both camps of internally displaced persons and villages with corresponding controls from both. Adverse events recorded in intervention group, but no data from control groups collected for adequate comparison.

			<p>Artesunate (60mg/20mg) daily for 3 days</p> <p>- Ages 4-10 years: 1 tablet Pyronaridine tetraphosphate and Artesunate (180mg/60mg) daily for 3 days</p> <p>- Ages 11-14 years: 2 tablets Pyronaridine tetraphosphate and Artesunate (180mg/60mg), daily for three days</p> <p>- Ages ≥ 15 years: 3 tablets Pyronaridine tetraphosphate and Artesunate (180mg/60mg) daily for 3 days</p>				
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Certainty of Evidence

Components of GRADE	Risk of Bias Domains	Judgment	Justification
Risk of Bias	Eligibility	Low risk	Eligibility criteria clearly defined: All people ages > 2 months except pregnant women in first trimester, people with severe malaria, jaundice, or other severe disease, people with an allergy to the drug being used for MDA, and people recently treated for malaria.
	Exposure Measurement	Unclear risk	Possibility of in/out migration between areas.
	Outcome: Mortality	Low risk	Reporting deaths of household members not highly likely to be biased.
	Control for Confounding	Unclear risk	Non-randomized, controlled interventional study.
	Follow-up	Low risk	Data collected from large cross-sectional survey.
	Overall	Downgraded	Unclear risk of bias in exposure measurement and control for confounding.
Inconsistency		-	
Indirectness		-	
Imprecision		-	
Publication Bias		-	

Excluded Studies

Light blue highlights articles including contextual factors, light yellow highlights articles presenting operational parameters through modeling.

Study Author (location, year)	Emergency Setting	Study design	MDA Intervention		Study population	Outcomes reported	Reason Excluded
			Rounds, interval	Population targeted (estimated coverage*)			
Houel, G. (Morocco, 1954 [23])	Malaria outbreak	Longitudinal measurements of cohort	1 round pyrimethamine	Undefined	147 children	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Malaria prevalence by blood smear • Splenic measurements 	Study design: no control, insufficient points for ITS
Clyde, DF; Webbe, G; Shute, GT (Tanganyika, 1958 [24])	Malaria outbreak	Longitudinal measurements of cohort	1 dose pyrimethamine (not given synchronously)	400 laborers (82% received first dose; 27% received second dose)	156 treated laborers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Malaria prevalence by blood smear 	MDA not provided as defined in methods
Lakshmanacharyulu, T. Guha A. K. Kache S. R. (India, 1961 [25])	Malaria outbreak	Longitudinal measurements of open cohort	2 rounds chloroquine and pyrimethamine given 3 months apart	28,000 laborers (~80%)	Surrounding community (~35,000)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Malaria incidence by blood smear 	Sub-therapeutic dose administered (no doses provided); no control for co-complemented interventions

Baukapur, S. N.; Babu, C. J. (India, 1984 [26])	Malaria outbreak	Longitudinal measurements of open cohort	Chloroquine (unspecified rounds, presumed one)	10,270 (76%)	10,270	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Malaria incidence by blood smear 	Sub-therapeutic dose administered (no doses provided); precise dates for MDA not provided to interpret data; no control for co-implemented interventions
Saarinen, M. <i>et al.</i> (Angola, 1987 [27])	Conflict	Non-randomized controlled trial	Proguanil daily for 4 months after initial presumptive chloroquine therapy	484 children in refugee camp aged 5 months to 5 years (100%)	484 children in intervention group; 268 children in nearby community as control	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Malaria prevalence by blood smear • Hospital admissions • Incidence of fever 	MDA not provided -- chemoprophylaxis
Zhang, Hong-Wei <i>et al.</i> (China, 2006 [28])	Malaria outbreak	Longitudinal measurements of open cohort	Chloroquine plus primaquine (doses and rounds not specified, presumed one round)	80,438 in 2006 and 59,457 in 2007	Residents of Huang-Huai Plain (population not specified)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Malaria incidence (confirmation not specified) 	Design: insufficient data points for ITS; No control
Kasereka, C. M.; Katsuva, J. P. M.; Hawkes, M. (DRC, 2014 [21])	Conflict	Uncontrolled cross sectional survey	None	N/A	Mugunga IDP camp	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of malaria cases identified in active screening campaign • Cost effectiveness of different screening techniques 	MDA not provided, outcomes out of scope of review

Walker <i>et al.</i> (Guinea, Liberia & Sierra Leone [22])	Ebola outbreak	Modeling	Dihydroartemisinin–piperazine or artesunate-amodiaquine, variable rounds and start dates	Populations of Guinea, Liberia, and Sierra Leone	NA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Expected malaria cases and deaths in several simulated scenarios 	Design: modeling; outcomes out of scope of review
Kuehne <i>et al.</i> (Liberia, 2016 [20])	Ebola outbreak	Uncontrolled cross sectional surveys	2 rounds artesunate amodiaquine given at one month interval	558,483 (94%)	Systematic sample of households receiving MDA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Self-reported incidence of fever • Adverse effects • Adherence/reasons for noncompliance 	Design: insufficient data points for ITS; No control
Bertozzi-Villa, A. <i>et al.</i> (Myanmar, 2017 [29])	N/A	Modeling	Not specified	Not specified	Not specified	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Impact of migration on MDA effectiveness 	Outcomes out of scope of review
Garbern, S. C. <i>et al.</i> (Liberia & Sierra Leone, 2018 [30])	Ebola outbreak	Retrospective cohort	2 rounds artesunate-amodiaquine given with 5 week interval	3,030,532 (90%)	424 individuals with Ebola seen at treatment facility	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ebola-related symptoms and mortality 	Outcomes out of scope of review